

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28

Systematic discovery of cell and immune function in IBD: Tnfsf8.

Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
East Islip, NY USA 11730

Tnfsf8 was activated in response to pattern recognition of MDP but this induction was lost in SNP13 homozygotes. SNP8/SNP13 heterozygotes in contrast retained *Tnfsf8* induction capacity which was instead hyperactivate; this was absent in SNP8/SNP12 heterozygotes.